

ISSUES OF MAINTAINING PUBLIC ORDER IN THE SYSTEM OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the issues of maintaining public order and ensuring public safety in our country. In ensuring public order, personnel management, effective use of force and means, crime prevention and crime prevention are organized. In this regard, the goal of the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025" plays an important role, in which the improvement of the legal framework for ensuring public security is to introduce a qualitatively new public security system in the country, to develop measures to develop the legal framework of the industry. Also, in order to increase the effectiveness of activities to ensure public safety, the organization of existing forces, the proper organization, coordination and management of their activities were separately considered.

Key words: Protecting public order, ensuring public safety, rights and freedoms, legal support for public safety activities, logistical support for public safety activities, training personnel for public safety activities.

Glorifying human dignity, ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of everyone has become a priority of the reforms being implemented in our country.

As our President noted, "Of course, human dignity is not some abstract, high-flown concept for us. When we speak of human dignity, we primarily mean the peaceful and safe life of every citizen, ensuring their fundamental rights and freedoms" [3].

"Today we are building a new state of Uzbekistan, a free civil society based on people's and democratic principles." To this end, we prioritize strengthening peace and stability, which are our priceless wealth, as the most important task" [2].

It is well known that the peaceful and safe life of citizens, ensuring their fundamental rights and freedoms, and ensuring public safety largely depend on the effective organization of activities. In the research works conducted in this regard, it is noted that "ensuring public safety is one of the stable, important, and mandatory elements of the state's existence" [22; 161-b], "ensuring public safety has always been the primary activity of the state, particularly its law enforcement agencies" [23; 91], "ensuring public safety is the most important issue on the agenda for developing the state's law enforcement system" [24; 167-b], we can agree with the conclusions presented.

Over the past period, completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing work to ensure public safety in our country based on the principle of "Serving the interests of the people" have been introduced, and purposeful interaction between state bodies and public structures has been established.

In the implementation of reforms aimed at further improving the public security system and increasing its efficiency, priority areas were defined as: "Clearly defining promising directions of state policy in the field of public security [5], forming an integrated public security

system, establishing effective activities from the lowest level of the system to the national level, strengthening law and order and legality in the country through the introduction of modern working methods, and ensuring the peace and tranquility of the population" [4].

Within the framework of reforms implemented in this area at the initiative of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, issues such as creating effective mechanisms for providing services to the population and interaction with the general public in ensuring public safety, increasing the efficiency of sector services by providing them with next-generation technologies and software systems, and organizing (modeling) service activities based on appropriate models have gained significant importance.

Based on the essence of the reforms being implemented in the field of ensuring public safety, we can consider their results by dividing them into the following directions.

Legal support for public safety activities. It is well known that one of the main features of the effective organization of activity is the legal regulation of its goals, tasks, and functions. Norms strengthen the legal status and functions of the subject and object of management, and increase the responsibility of each participant in the management system of society [21; 14].

An analysis of the reforms carried out in recent years in the field of ensuring public safety shows that in this process, special attention is paid to creating the legal foundations of activities based on modern requirements.

In particular, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" initiated a new stage of reforms in the system by eliminating gaps, ambiguities, and contradictions in the legal framework regulating the highly responsible, multifaceted, and diverse activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as by ensuring the unification of the main provisions regarding the activities of internal affairs bodies within the framework of a separate law [26; P. 71].

The improvement of the legal framework for ensuring public safety provides for a clear delimitation of the tasks, functions, and responsibilities of the entities ensuring and participating in public safety [7], the elimination of duplicate and obsolete powers, the strengthening of the level of material and technical support for units ensuring operational efficiency, and the improvement of the quality of modern scientific, technical, and information-communication technologies, including public services [17; 11].

The Decree of the President of our country "On approval of the Concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" is primarily aimed at ensuring the peaceful life of the population within the framework of large-scale reforms in the country, as well as forming a culture of the rule of law and public safety in society. Until now, there were no full legal foundations in this regard. Based on this decree, the Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Strategy for the Development of the Public Safety System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025 were approved.

In the "Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan," an important document defining state policy in the field of ensuring public safety, which is considered one of the main directions of national security, important issues such as basic concepts related to public safety, national interests in the field of ensuring public safety, main directions of state policy, fundamental principles of activity, state regulation, mechanisms for implementing the concept, and expected results have been legally enshrined [5].

In this regard, it should be noted that until now, there have been a number of misconceptions about the true essence of the concept of public safety, and now its meaning,

clear and fluent rule has also been regulated on the basis of a legal document [16]. In particular, public safety is the state of protection of society from illegal encroachments, social and interethnic conflicts, emergencies, and other threats, which serves the sustainable development of society and ensures the realization of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests.

The goal of the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Safety System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025," which plays an important role in improving the legal framework for ensuring public safety, is to develop and effectively implement measures for the implementation of a qualitatively new system for ensuring public safety in the country and the development of the legal framework for the sector [27; 10]. In particular,

- unification of more than 200 normative-legal and departmental normative acts of authorized bodies responsible for this field by developing and adopting a unified draft law in the field of public safety;

- development and implementation of criteria and key indicators (indicators) that determine the status and levels of threats to public safety;

- further improvement of the security system at transport and tourism facilities, and the development and adoption of a draft unified legislative act defining the tasks and functions of state bodies and service entities in this field;

- through the development and adoption of a draft law regulating the rules for holding mass events, firstly, the development of departmental regulatory legal acts in the interests of a specific agency or the elimination of circumstances that impose obligations on other entities; secondly, the regulation of relations in the field of ensuring public safety by the relevant norms of a number of laws and bylaws, the development of mechanisms for the direct implementation of relations in this field; thirdly, the systematization of bylaws regulating public safety activities provides for the elimination of misunderstandings regarding the application of law in the performance of official activities by entities in this field, as well as the positive resolution of a number of legal issues awaiting resolution.

At the same time, as a way to overcome the sharp increase in traffic violations and the severe consequences of road traffic accidents, specific measures are being taken to strengthen liability measures for systematic violations of road safety rules and those who committed road traffic accidents with grave consequences, including the introduction of a criminal law measure in the form of long-term deprivation of the right to drive a vehicle, taking into account advanced foreign experience, the introduction of a procedure for recovering material damage from the heads of organizations or bodies in charge of road or engineering-communication infrastructure facilities whose unsatisfactory condition led to a road traffic accident, especially a death, and determining their liability, the introduction of administrative liability for actions expressed in "hooliganism on the road" committed by drivers of vehicles, and the improvement of legal mechanisms for holding pedestrians accountable for violating traffic rules [28; 239].

Management and organization of public safety activities. To increase the effectiveness of public security activities, it is necessary to organize existing forces, properly organize, coordinate, and manage their activities. In management theory, "management" is understood as the influence of a governing body (person-subject of management) on the governing bodies (persons-object of management), carried out within a specific system. This takes into account the characteristics and patterns of the relevant field, as well as the specific subordination of the

manager and the managed [31; 59]. Management is the manager's activity to ensure the effective functioning of the entire system [18; P. 29].

The management of public security activities is the executive and administrative activities of authorized state bodies and public organizations in this field [29; 2-b].

In legal literature, along with the term "management," the term "organization" is also used. According to legal scholars U. Tadjikhanov and S. Akhmedova, the general tasks of organizational management are actions aimed at developing and implementing specific measures to implement the adopted decision [19; P. 40].

In order to ensure peace and stability in the country through the implementation of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms based on the "republic - region - district - mahalla" system, and the effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs and other state bodies in ensuring public safety, the following completely new mechanisms have been implemented within the framework of ongoing reforms [4]:

first, the phased creation of mahalla law enforcement posts on the basis of internal affairs body strongpoints. In accordance with it, the mahalla law enforcement post is considered the main lower link in ensuring public safety, preventing offenses, and combating crime in the territory, and on its basis, the prevention inspector is tasked with the systematic organization and coordination of the coordinated activities of the relevant sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, the National Guard, and other state bodies, as well as the work of ensuring public safety;

secondly, in order to introduce a unified system of management and coordination of the activities of sectoral services for the protection of public order and ensuring security of internal affairs bodies by improving the structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Department of Public Security was established, and its main tasks were defined;

thirdly, in order to ensure the effective use of existing forces and resources by optimizing the structures and leadership positions of territorial internal affairs bodies for maintaining public order and ensuring security, the position of Deputy Head of the Public Security Service of territorial and subordinate internal affairs bodies was introduced through the abolition of certain leadership positions, and its main tasks were defined as coordinating the activities of patrol and road patrol service units, as well as conducting targeted preventive measures in mahallas and public places, working with persons previously convicted and placed on probation, and organizing night service.

Based on this, the lower levels of the internal affairs bodies were strengthened to strengthen work on maintaining public order, ensuring citizen safety, crime prevention, and combating crime in mahallas [14].

Within the framework of reforms, significant work is also being carried out to enhance the republic's tourism potential; specifically, comprehensive measures are being taken to create favorable conditions for tourists and to establish Uzbekistan's reputation as a safe country for visits [6].

As a result of reforms carried out in the field of management and organization of security activities at transport and tourism facilities, a unique national system for ensuring safe tourism has been formed. This system combines measures for maintaining public order, early prevention of offenses, and the fight against crime in tourist sites and at railway and air transport infrastructure facilities actively used by tourists to travel across the republic. This

contributed to the transition to a qualitatively new stage of effective public safety at transport and tourism facilities.

It is known that the system of organization and management of the activities of public safety units in the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region differs from the system of organization and management of units carrying out this activity in other administrative territories of the Republic.

Over the past period, significant work has been carried out in the capital of our country - the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region - to implement a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, crime prevention, and the fight against crime based on close cooperation between state bodies and civil society institutions, ensuring law and order and the reliable protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens [25; 68] [10].

In particular, in order to effectively organize the activities of public safety units in the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region, a new management system has been introduced, providing for:

first, a procedure has been introduced for ensuring public safety in the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region through the joint mobilization of the available forces and resources of all authorized bodies in these territories based on the principle of a single "capital region."

In order to effectively organize work based on the principle of a single "capital region," a Coordinating Council on Public Safety was established. It is envisaged that Council meetings will be held at least once a month, during which targeted measures will be determined for the joint resolution of problems identified as a result of the analysis of the criminogenic and social situation in the capital region;

secondly, a Unified Operational Management Center has been established under the Main Department of Internal Affairs of Tashkent, the main tasks of which are defined as:

- conducting continuous monitoring of the criminogenic and social situation in the capital's territory, and managing the relevant forces and resources of internal affairs bodies, the National Guard, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, and the Tashkent City Khokimiyat involved in ensuring public safety;

- to respond promptly to reports of crimes, incidents, and emergencies, and to centrally coordinate the actions of competent authorities in cases involving mass violations of public order [11].

An analysis of the reforms being implemented in the field of improving the management and organization of public security activities shows that special attention is paid to the widespread implementation of digitalization in this field.

It is well known that digitalization is a modern convenience that is penetrating all spheres and industries today. These facilities are currently being fully implemented in the public safety system. In the future, it is planned to maximize the reduction of paper records management in the field of public safety and increase the share of documents maintained in electronic form to 90 percent [15].

Furthermore, within the framework of implemented reforms, the use of new working methods in organizing activities based on the concepts of "Safe Capital," "Smooth and Safe Road," "Safe Household," "Safe Courtyard," "E-Patrol" systems, "Smart Mahalla," "E-Public Safety," and "Safe City" hardware and software complexes has proven to create many conveniences [30; 157-b].

Training of personnel for public safety activities. One of the most important measures to ensure public safety is the provision of personnel who are aware of modern science and technology for the operation of this field based on specific mechanisms.

The reforms carried out in this direction based on the relevant decisions of the President include, firstly, the organization of a system for training highly qualified specialists in the field of ensuring public safety based on advanced international standards; secondly, increasing the human resource potential of units in this field based on modern requirements [13]; thirdly, ensuring the professional growth of employees depending on their qualifications; and fourthly, further increasing the intellectual and professional potential of management personnel in the effective management of forces and resources [12].

As a result of the reforms carried out to improve the personnel training system for public security activities, firstly, as a result of the fundamental reform of the educational process at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the introduction of a two-stage system of higher education (bachelor's and master's degrees) and targeted training mechanisms for management personnel, further increasing the intellectual and professional potential of management personnel in the effective management of forces and means of ensuring public security; secondly, the introduction of a continuous training and career system, which includes a procedure for the educational process closely linked to the rules of service [8], ensuring the professional growth of employees depending on their qualifications in the public security system; thirdly, the introduction of a system for the targeted training of qualified personnel in the field of public security allows for the training, retraining, and advanced training of officer specialists in the areas of public order protection, road safety, and the implementation of passport system requirements, which are considered the main units of the sector.

Based on the requirements of the times, the University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established to increase the human resource potential of law enforcement agencies and the Armed Forces.

The university has been designated as a basic higher military educational and research institution for the targeted training of qualified personnel. For the first time in the country's history, a unique opportunity was created at the university for young people to study at a higher military educational institution on a general civil basis, and girls were admitted to study in the military field [16].

Material and technical support for public safety activities. There are a number of factors influencing the effectiveness of public safety activities, among which material and technical support plays an important role [20; 11]. To date, there is no sphere of human activity in which positive changes have not occurred as a result of the introduction of modern technologies. Currently, innovative technologies are rapidly developing and penetrating into all spheres of our lives, which, along with other spheres of society, imposes tasks on the introduction of new innovative techniques and technologies into the activities of ensuring public safety and increasing competitiveness through the use of high technologies.

In this regard, the President's words "when introducing a number of changes in the field, it is necessary, first of all, to improve the modern material and technical base of services on the streets and in public places based on advanced foreign experience" [1; 334-b] serves as a guide to action. In particular, within the framework of the ongoing reforms, the establishment of service by employees with a personal video recorder (body camera), the provision of intelligent cameras ("Smart") with the ability to observe and independently control, the registration and

consideration of cases of offenses with electronic system tablets, equipment and technologies such as special cars and motorcycles designed for patrolling, allows to save the time of employees, increase the mobility of forces and means, ensure the inevitability of punishment in a timely and prompt manner, prevent corruption, promptly manage forces and means and respond to citizens' appeals.

In today's era of globalization, new threats and dangers are emerging, and the methods, means, and goals of committing crimes are changing. In this sense, it can be said that along with the achievements made, there are important priorities planned for further improvement of the effectiveness of ensuring public safety.

These priority areas determine the prospects for increasing the efficiency of public safety activities.

In this regard, documents such as the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Safety System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2025," developed based on advanced foreign and national experience in ensuring public safety and aimed at the guaranteed protection of the population from any threats, and the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026," adopted to determine priority areas for reforms aimed at further increasing the well-being of our people and unconditionally ensuring human rights and interests based on the principle of "For Human Dignity," are of great importance.

In accordance with the 16th goal of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" (Ensuring public safety, creating an effective system for the timely identification and elimination of conditions contributing to the commission of offenses), in terms of bringing the crime prevention system to a qualitatively new level and fundamentally improving the activities of the patrol service for maintaining public order; In accordance with Goal 17 (Forming a new image of law enforcement agencies and directing their activities toward the effective protection of public interests, human dignity, rights, and freedoms), a series of measures are being implemented to transform internal affairs bodies into a people-oriented professional structure as a reliable defender of the people and to focus on targeted work with the population, as well as to make the principle of "Law is supreme, punishment is inevitable" the main criterion [6].

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of reforms aimed at further improving the system of ensuring public safety and increasing its efficiency, the state of protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the interests of society and the state from illegal encroachments will be raised to a qualitatively high level.

In ensuring public safety, increasing public trust in authorized state bodies for ensuring public safety is achieved by directing the service activities of employees toward assisting citizens.

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